

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF VALUE'S IN PRIMARY AND SECONDARY SCHOOL CHILDREN.

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Introduction: Education takes us to the top, but VBE takes the whole society to the top. Education gives us capacity of better learning, but VBE gives us the tool for a deeper understanding too; education gives us *Anna* but VBE provides us *Ananda too*; education may bring limitations but VBE is for liberation. After all right education means- "*Sa Vidya Ya Vimuktaye*". It means that *knowledge* is what helps us to attain liberation.

VBE is highly needed in our modern society because our lives have become more miserable. The quantity of education has considerably increased, but the quality has decreased. Why? The number of educated people - *Paper presented in a Workshop organized by Save The Children and Curriculum Development Centre on 29th December, 2009* has reached at a high level, but murder, hatred, and selfishness have spread out like wildfire everywhere. Why? Many institutions are opened, but only few civilized people are produced. Why? Degrees are available for all, but the dignity has gone down. Why? Trained people are produced from many institutions, but sincere people are very few. Why? Many books are written; much research is done; many professional achievements are attained, but humanity is threatened. Why? Therefore, we need VBE.

The rate of suicide is going up in our society. One of the very common factors responsible for this is over pressure on students to get the high marks in their exams. It is for sure a very unhealthy and unethical competition. It is not only limited to a school level education, several suicide cases happen even at top level academic institutions worldwide. The highest purpose of education is now either disregarded or may be forgotten. The Vedas say - "*Etat Desh Prasutasya Sakasat Agrajanman, Swam Swam Charitram Shiksheran Prithivyam Sarva Manava...*" It means that people who are born in this part of the earth should enlighten the entire world by presenting the example of their own character. Is there any difference between primary and second Schools in imparting value education? Is it to be taught in the schools? Is there in the home and society ample chances for acquiring value education? The investigator tried to study these thought provoking questions and come to the conclusion.

Statement of the problem: A Comparative study of Value in Primary and Secondary school children in Nandurbar city.

Objectives of research:

1. To find out the significant difference of value education between primary and secondary children.
2. To find out the significant difference of value education between primary boys and primary girls.
3. To find out the significant difference of value education between secondary boys and secondary girls.

Hypothesis: In the present study the investigator has proposed the following hypothesis for testing the results.

1. There is no significant difference between value education in primary and secondary children.
2. There is no significant difference between value education in primary boys and primary girls.
3. There is no significant difference between value education in secondary boys and secondary girls.

Methodology For the present research work researcher was selected Descriptive Survey method.

Population of the study Primary and secondary school student in the Akola city in the Maharashtra state

Sampling The investigator used stratified random sampling techniques. 80 from primary and 80 from secondary school Student.

Tool use For the said research work the investigator used self made Value Education inventory.

Statistical Technique Mean, SD and ‘t’ Ratio used for data analysis

Table – 1: Descriptive analysis

Primary School Boys		Primary School Girls	
Range and scores	No of Children	Range and scores	No of Children
61 and above	8	61 and above	9
45 – 60	9	45 – 60	6
25 – 44	7	25 – 44	8
13 – 24	8	13 – 24	7
0 – 12	8	0 – 12	10
Secondary School Boys:		Secondary School Girls	
Range and scores	No of Children	Range and scores	No of Children
61 and above	6	61 and above	9
45 – 60	9	45 – 60	7
25 – 44	8	25 – 44	6
13 – 24	9	13 – 24	9
0- 12	8	0 – 12	9

In this way the data was presented in the form of scores and number of children obtained those scores. After wards the statistical tolls were calculated.

Table – 2

Hypothesis – 1

There is no significant difference between primary and secondary school students in value education.

Group	N	Mean	S.D.	‘t’	Significance level
Primary	80	163.66	10.11	8.62	Significant at 0.05 level
Secondary	80	150.98	8.50		

Observations:

1. As per statistical table for *df* 118 at 0.05 significant level sample ‘t’ was 1.9 and obtained ‘t’ was 8.62
2. In present research obtained ‘t’ 8.62 was more than sample ‘t’ hence obtained ‘t’ is significant.
3. Thus there was significant difference of value education between primary and secondary school students.

Result:

The mean of value education for primary students was 163.66 and that of secondary students was 150.98. So the difference was 12.68 hence there was a better value system for primary students than secondary students.

**Table – 3
Hypothesis – 2**

There is no significant difference between primary school boys and girls in value education.

Group	N	Mean	S.D.	Df	‘t’	Significance level
Primary Boys	40	167.41	11.68	78	3.22	Significant at 0.05 level
Primary Girls	40	159.87	9.11			

Observations:

1. As per statistical table for *df* 78 at 0.05 significant level sample ‘t’ was 1.9 and obtained ‘t’ was 3.22.
2. In present research obtained ‘t’ 3.22 was more than sample ‘t’ hence obtained ‘t’ is significant.
3. Thus there was significant difference of value education between primary school boys and girls. Hence the formed hypothesis was rejected and in the new hypothesis there will be significant difference of value education between primary boys and girls was accepted.

Result:

The mean of value education for primary boys was 167.41 and that of girls 159.87 so the difference was 7.54 Hence there was a better value system for primary boys than girls.

**Table – 4
Hypothesis – 3**

There is no significant difference between secondary school boys and girls in value education.

Group	N	Mean	S.D.	df	't'	Significance level
Secondary Boys	40	151.21	8.7	78	3.23	Significant at 0.05 level
Secondary Girls	40	157.75	9.4			

Observations:

1. As per statistical table for df 78 at 0.05 significant level sample 't' was 1.9 and obtained 't' was 3.23.
2. In present research obtained 't' 3.23 was more than sample's hence obtained 't' is significant.
3. Thus there was significant difference of value education between secondary school boys and girls. Hence the formed hypothesis was rejected and the new hypothesis there will be significant difference of value education between secondary boys and girls was accepted.

Result:

The mean of value education for secondary school girls was 157.75 and that of boys was 151.21. So the difference was 5.54. Hence there was a better value system for secondary school girls than boys.

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